

OUTLINING AND FIVE W'S AND H: ITS EFFECT TO WRITING PROFICIENCY OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the effect of Outlining and Five W's and H strategies in the writing proficiency of grade 11 Students. This study utilized two-group pretest posttest experimental research design which identifies whether using the outlining and five W's and H strategies has an effect in the writing proficiency of senior high school students. The weighted mean and standard deviation used to assess the pre and post writing proficiency of the respondents. T-test was used to determine if there is a significant difference between the Writing strategies and the student's writing proficiency. After the analysis, the study found out that outlining and five W's and H strategies was assessed to be effective in the writing proficiency of the respondents in terms to conventions, syntax and vocabulary. And also, the study found out that these strategies has something to do with the writing proficiency of the respondents. In terms of the pretest and posttest of the students in using the strategies it can be inferred that the Writing Strategies has effectively contributed to the Writing Proficiency of the students based on the result of their tests performances. Based on the findings, it was concluded that using writing strategies is effective in enhancing the respondent's writing proficiency. There is a significant relationship between the pretest and posttest performances of the respondents in their writing proficiency before and after using the outlining and Five W's and H strategies. There is a significant relationship between the posttest performances of the respondents in their writing proficiency in the experimental group 1 and 2 before and after using the Outlining and Five W's and H strategies.

Keywords: Outlining, Five W's and H, Writing Proficiency, Conventions, Vocabulary, Syntax